

Annex 6.1. Decisions taken by the Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity at its 15th and 16th meetings referencing the financial system, categorized according to whether their objective is Greening Finance (yellow), Financing Green (light green) or both (dark green).

Decision	Section	Contents	Objective
Decision 15/4 (CBD, 2022c)	Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, target 15	Take legal, administrative or policy measures to encourage and enable businesses, and in particular to ensure that large and transnational companies and financial institutions:	Greening finance
		(a) Regularly monitor, assess, and transparently disclose their risks, dependencies and impacts on biodiversity, including with requirements for all large as well as transnational companies and financial institutions along their operations, supply and value chains, and portfolios;	
		(b) Provide information needed to consumers to promote sustainable consumption patterns;	
		(c) Report on compliance with access and benefit-sharing regulations and measures, as applicable;	
		in order to progressively reduce negative impacts on biodiversity, increase positive impacts, reduce biodiversity-related risks to businesses and financial institutions, and promote actions to ensure sustainable patterns of production.	
Decision 15/7 (CBD, 2022b)	Resource mobilization	16. Calls for fundamental transformation of the global financial architecture and the reform of multilateral development banks and international finance institutions, including investment banks, to make them fit for purpose in supporting implementation of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, sustainable development and just transition efforts in developing countries.	Greening finance

		17. Invites multilateral development banks as well as international financial institutions and philanthropy, to support the strategy for resource mobilization, and in particular to:	Greening finance & financing green
		(a) Identify and report investments in their portfolio that contribute to achieving the objectives of the Convention and the goals and targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, taking into account relevant international guidance and good international practice;	
		(b) Align their portfolios and financial flows with the objectives of the Convention, and the goals and targets of Framework by 2030;	
		(c) Simplify access to financial resources for biodiversity;	
		(d) Increase biodiversity funding, through leveraging financial resources from all sources and deploying a full suite of instruments, including new and innovative approaches such as private capital mobilization and blended finance.	
		18. Invites international financial institutions and multilateral development banks, in particular the World Bank Group and the International Monetary Fund, to immediately consider supporting implementation of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, including by partnering with the Global Biodiversity Framework Fund, established as per paragraph 30 of the present decision.	Financing green
Resource mobilization - review of the strategy	36. Requests the Global Environmental Facility to engage all multilateral development banks and other international financial institutions in the design and operationalization of the Global Biodiversity Framework Fund, with the view of leveraging additional resources from and for the Fund and channel them through new and existing biodiversity portfolios, which need to be aligned with the goals and targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework.	Financing green	
	1. Increase international biodiversity-related financial flows and financial resources from all sources	Financing green	

		<p>(a) Increase biodiversity-related international financial resource flows to developing countries, in particular least developed countries and small island developing States, as well as countries with economies in transition:</p>	<p style="background-color: #c8e6c9; padding: 5px;">Greening finance & financing green</p>	
<p>(i) Fulfilment of developed country Parties' obligations to provide adequate, new and additional financial resources;</p>	<p>(ii) Other Parties to consider whether they may voluntarily assume the obligations of the developed country Parties;</p>	<p>(iii) Increase international biodiversity funding by multilateral development banks, international financial institutions and philanthropy, in partnership with the Global Environment Facility, as appropriate;</p>		
<p>(c) Mobilize additional international resources, including</p>	<p>(i) By increasing innovative finance solutions, such as green bonds and payments for ecosystem services, and developing guidelines and sharing good practices;</p>	<p>(ii) Through philanthropy and businesses and leveraging private finance.</p>		
<p>2. Identify and eliminate, phase out, or reform financial resource flows causing harm</p>	<p>(a) Mainstream biodiversity in development cooperation:</p>	<p>(i) Re-prioritize portfolios and practices of development cooperation agencies and banks, multilateral development banks, international financial institutions and charities, with a view to aligning financial flows with the objectives of the Convention;</p>		<p style="background-color: #43a047; color: white; padding: 5px;">Greening finance & financing green</p>
<p>(ii) Harness and scale synergies in project development and financing with a view to generating and increasing biodiversity co-benefits.</p>	<p>(b) Strengthen risk assessment and transparent reporting requirement of international private finance and business actors.</p>			

		(c) Report on actions taken and efforts made to identify and eliminate, phase out, or reform harmful incentives.	
		<p>3. Enhance the effectiveness of resource use</p> <p>(a) Improve Global Environment Facility operations and access modalities, including by developing fast-track systems; by allowing the Global Environment Facility Trust Fund to be open to contributions from all sources, including from the private sector and from philanthropy; and by putting in place institutional arrangements for the trust fund in partnership with multilateral development banks and international financial institutions;</p> <p>(b) Simplify access modalities for biodiversity funding of multilateral development banks, international financial institutions and charities;</p> <p>(c) Increase transparency and accountability, monitoring and reporting, of biodiversity-related public and private financing at all levels;</p> <p>(d) Direct more resources to key implementation partners at the regional, national and local levels and facilitate partnerships to ensure community engagement and results on the ground;</p> <p>(e) Strengthen ownership and capacity to access funding;</p> <p>(f) Build synergies and harness biodiversity co-benefits.</p>	Greening finance & financing green
Decision 15/11 (CBD, 2022d)	Gender plan of action	10. Invites the Global Environment Facility and relevant bilateral and multilateral funding organizations to provide technical and financial support, as well as capacity-building and development, for implementation of the Gender plan of action.	Financing green
Decision 15/15 (CBD, 2022e)	Financial mechanism – Global Biodiversity Framework Fund	26. Requests the Global Environment Facility to engage all multilateral development banks and other international financial institutions in the design and operationalization of the Global Biodiversity Framework Fund, with the view of leveraging additional resources from and for the fund and channel them through new and existing biodiversity portfolios, which need to be aligned with the goals and targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework.	Financing green
Decision 16/33 (CBD/COP, 2025a)	Financial mechanism – Global Biodiversity Framework Fund	16. Regrets the lack of contributions from the private and financial sectors, philanthropic organizations, non-governmental organizations and other stakeholders to the Global Biodiversity Framework Fund and requests the Global Environment	Financing green

		Facility and the Council of the Global Biodiversity Framework Fund to explore ways to enhance resource mobilization and report on progress to the Conference of the Parties at its seventeenth meeting.	
		19. <i>Also welcomes</i> the fact that 25 per cent of the resources of the Global Biodiversity Framework Fund is to be programmed through international financial institutions that are agencies of the Global Environment Facility.	Financing green
Decision 16/34 (CBD/COP, 2025b)	Resource mobilization	5. Encourages all Parties, other Governments, organizations, multilateral development banks, the private sector and other stakeholders to use the strategy as flexible guidance in mobilizing new and additional resources from all sources and aligning financial flows to implement the Convention and its Protocols as well as to achieve the Goals and the Targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, commensurate with their ambition.	Financing green
		9. Urges Parties, the private sector, financial institutions and multilateral development banks to put in place and enforce social and environmental safeguards and apply a human rights-based approach in developing or scaling up biodiversity and finance instruments, in particular for innovative schemes, in line with the voluntary guidelines for safeguards in biodiversity financing mechanisms in annex III to decision XII/3 of 17 October 2014 and decision 14/15 of 29 November 2018.	Financing green
		20. Recognizes that, in addition to and in support of, the Strategy on Resource Mobilization, the actions outlined below can further contribute to addressing the global biodiversity finance gap: (a) Enhance the coordination among, complementarity of, and enabling conditions for, the instruments across the global biodiversity finance landscape, harnessing synergies, such as with multilateral development banks;	Financing green
	Resource mobilization - Annex I Strategy for resource mobilization for the period 2025–2030/ I. Enabling actions	4. The strategy can be enabled by the following possible actions: (i) Encouraging multilateral development banks and, as applicable, other national and international financial institutions that are active in this field, to continue and intensify, to the extent possible, their work on environmental and social safeguards and on developing and refining common methodologies, principles and guidelines for tracking, disclosing and reporting in a harmonized way on, their biodiversity investments and impacts, in line with relevant mandates and in a manner supportive	Greening finance

		<p>of the achievement of sustainable development and poverty eradication. (j) Encouraging, as applicable, national, and international financial institutions, including national central banks and/or other regulatory authorities to identify and assess the biodiversity related opportunities, challenges, financial risks, and impacts in line with relevant mandates and in a manner supportive of the achievement of sustainable development and poverty eradication.</p>	
		<p>5. New and additional resources are mobilized with a view to achieving target 19 (a) of the Framework, through, inter alia: (d) increased investments by multilateral development banks and other relevant international financial institutions in their portfolios that contribute to achieving the objectives of the Convention and its Protocols as well as the goals and targets of the Framework, in line with their mandates and in a manner supportive of achieving sustainable development and poverty eradication.</p>	Financing green
		<p>8. Public and private financial resource flows causing harm to biodiversity can be identified and eliminated, phased out, redirected, or reformed and progressively aligned with the goals and targets of the Framework by: (a) Mainstreaming biodiversity in development cooperation by encouraging, to the extent possible, and in line with their respective mandates, to adjust the portfolios and practices of development cooperation agencies and banks, multilateral development banks, international financial institutions and philanthropic organizations, with a view to progressively align their financial flows, in line with target 14 of the Framework, in a manner supportive of the achievement of sustainable development, including poverty eradication efforts;</p>	Greening finance
		<p>9. The uptake, accessibility, effectiveness, efficiency, transparency and accountability in resource provision and use can be enhanced by: (b) Simplifying access modalities for biodiversity funding of international financial institutions, including multilateral development banks, as well as philanthropic organizations, in particular for Indigenous Peoples and local communities, women and youth;</p>	Financing green

		12. Financial resource flows causing harm to biodiversity can be identified and eliminated, phased out, or reformed and aligned with the goals and targets of the Framework, by: (c) Mainstreaming biodiversity, as appropriate, into the policies of national central banks or other regulatory authorities, taking relevant distinct mandates into account.	Greening finance
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